

Short Communication

Biochemical effect of chronic doses of carbamate and fenvalerate on liver and muscles of freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus* (Bloch).

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Abstract: The present investigation deals with biochemical effect of chronic doses of carbamate and fenvalerate administered continuously for 60 days on liver and muscles of freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus*. Treatment with carbamate increases the value of Cholesterol by 3.63% and 18.54% in liver and muscle respectively. While increases the value of triglycerides by 5.31% and 4.81% in liver and muscle respectively. Treatment with fenvalerate increases the value of Cholesterol by 4.02% and 22.45% in liver and muscle respectively. While increases the value of triglycerides by 5.73% and 4.65% in liver and muscle respectively. This shows the alterations in biochemical parameters in liver and muscles due to liver cirrhosis and toxicant accumulation in muscles.

Key Words: Carbamate, Fenvalerate, *Channa punctatus*, Liver, Muscle, Cholesterol, Triglycerides

Introduction

India is an over populated country with its high growth rate. The country mainly depends on agricultural products to feed its people. So a large amount of agro-chemicals and insecticides are used to enhance the agricultural production from a limited land to meet the demand of food grains for country's ever increasing population. Every year about thousands metric ton of insecticides are being used in agricultural fields. It is assumed that 25% of these used pesticides drain off into open water bodies through rainfall and floods (Anonymous, 1994). As a result aquatic environment obviously gets polluted. The pollution hazards for aquatic life are increasing significantly. Sometimes their extreme pollution may cause sudden death of fish and other aquatic organisms.

Organophosphate and carbamate have replaced organochlorine pesticides because of their rapid breakdown in the water and their low environmental persistence. However, these insecticides used in intensive agricultural production reach the aquatic environment either *via* sewage or directly due to the spraying against pests (Castillo *et al.*, 1997). Fenvalerate synthesized by Ohno *et al.*, (1976) using 3-phenoxy benzaldehyde cynohydrin and 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-methylbutyric acid, is one of the recent pyrethroid being used for pest control.

Relatively short half-life and rapid degradation (Ohkawa *et al.*, 1978) have also made fenvalerate a much more effective insecticide. Another aspect of fenvalerate metabolism, which is not found in other pyrethroids, is a unique path of degradation, i.e., ether cleavage that retains the ester intact.

Bioaccumulation of xenobiotics including insecticides in aquatic species is increasing alarmingly, thus posing a threat to aquatic life. A variety of fish species show uptake and accumulation of many contaminants such as pesticides (Heger *et al.*, 1995; Siddiqui *et al.*, 2005), polychlorinated biphenyls (Guiney and Peterson, 1980), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Tuvikene, 1995); heavy metals (Rajan *et al.*, 1995). Pesticides have been found to be highly toxic not only to fishes, but also to fish food organisms, thus threatening the life of fish (Grande *et al.*, 1994; Singh *et al.*, 2007).

Liver is a main site of synthesis and detoxification whereas muscles are the main part of consumption as a food. Any toxicants affecting the liver will ultimately disturb the fish metabolism. The pesticides being lipophilic in nature get accumulated in muscles and contaminated the next trophic level when other organisms consume the fish. It is important therefore, to evaluate the toxicity of newly marketed pesticides on fish, as they form an important part of human food. The snakehead, *Channa punctatus* locally